

TYPES OF RUBRICS ON ASSESSING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS

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Abstract. This article highlights a number of questions that might arise as we develop our productive skills assessment tasks. We begin by suggesting a number of task types that might be useful in the classroom.

Keywords: communicative competence, language knowledge, speech skills, structure and content of the test, method, test sections.

INTRODUCTION

In order to assess learners' productive skills, you will need to develop assessment tasks that allow learners to demonstrate real-world speaking and writing skills – that will be useful in their interactions outside of the classroom.

We should pay attention to choose a Task Type (TT). We have as many options for task types as there are speaking and writing opportunities in the real world.

1. Role play is any speaking activity when you either put yourself into somebody else's shoes, or when you stay in your own shoes but put yourself into an imaginary situation! Role-play can be a lot of fun. If you still feel reluctant to use it in the class, I suggest you begin to integrate it slowly.

2. Story-telling describes the social and cultural activity of sharing stories, sometimes with improvisation, theatrics or embellishment. Every culture has its own stories or narratives, which are shared as a means of entertainment, education, cultural preservation or instilling moral values.

3. Small group discussion allows presenters to announce a topic or idea for group discussion among participants. A small-group discussion follows democratic guidelines and allows everyone to contribute many ideas for others to discuss and reflect upon.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Productive language skills, speaking and writing, are important because they are the observable evidence of language acquisition. The more the speaker or the writer produces appropriate and coherent language the more we have proof of the progress in the learner's language system. Teaching productive skills is also important because written and spoken communication are basic life skills. In real life, people generally may need to inform, convince or share ideas. They are also sometimes required to take notes, fill in forms, and write emails,

letters, reports or stories.

Unlike the receptive skills lesson plan, in addition to understanding and interpreting the discourse, a productive skills lesson aims at helping learners produce appropriate and coherent messages either in spoken or written forms. It is true that making sense of, and being able to process, the input is important, but what is essentially involved in the productive skills is the ability to convey information, convince or share ideas and feelings.

Task Outline:

Write a letter to a close friend about your summer vacation. In your letter you should include the followings:

- How and with whom you spend your summer vacation;
- Where you went;
- How did you feel during the vacation?

Answer all the bullet points with at least 150 words.

Standard based on CEFR:

- ◆ Category A: **Social and Tourist**
- ◆ Concern: **Personal contacts (at a distance)**
- ◆ Activity: **writing letters**
- ◆ Environment: **Home, away from home**

CEF B1 (ALTE 2): CAN write letters of a routine nature. CAN write simple letters relating facts and events.

The Holistic rubric for assessing Writing and Grammar and Language Use skills of B1

Assessment scoring	Criteria: Content
4 - Excellent	The letter effectively communicates the writer's summer vacation plans with rich detail and enthusiasm. It includes relevant information about activities, destinations, and individual experiences. The letter demonstrates a strong command of grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure appropriate for a B1 level. There are few to no errors, and the language flows smoothly.

3 - Good	The letter adequately communicates the writer's summer vacation plans with some detail and enthusiasm. It includes relevant information about activities and destinations but may lack depth. The letter demonstrates a good command of grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure appropriate for a B1 level. There may be occasional minor errors, but they do not impede understanding
2 - Fair	The letter partially communicates the writer's summer vacation plans with limited detail and enthusiasm. It includes some relevant information but lacks coherence or organization. The letter demonstrates a fair command of grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure appropriate for a B1 level. There are noticeable errors that occasionally impede understanding
1 - Poor	The letter does not effectively communicate the writer's summer vacation plans. It lacks detail, coherence, and relevance to the topic. The letter demonstrates a poor command of grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure. Errors are frequent and significantly impede understanding.

Justification: A structured framework for evaluating students' writing proficiency in informal letters about summer vacations at the B1 level can be created by connecting **rubrics** to the **Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) standards**. When evaluating the **Writing skill** and **Language use**, holistic rubrics are a particularly useful tool for **B1-Intermediate students**. The assessment of the students' writing skills is thorough and concentrates more on the **overall quality than on detailed elements of the language**. Such rubrics emphasize clear communication, helping lower tension and promote advancement. Additionally, while recognizing the learners' continuous improvement, they can offer a **realistic assessment** of the learners' skills. Considering all, holistic rubrics can offer an adequate method of language learning that can accelerate language acquisition facilitating an efficient communication. Weigle (2012) highlighted that **Writing**

is a crucial support skill for students at **lower levels** of instruction, particularly in foreign language contexts, where **simple tasks** and **specific language items** should be used to practice structures and vocabulary.

Therefore the preferred assessment tool- **Holistic rubrics** can allow students to be evaluated on their overall communicative effectiveness in expressing their summer vacation experiences.

According to **CEFR B1- Intermediate language level's ALTE CAN DO PROJECT**, students should be able to write **basic, related texts about well-known subjects** while sharing their own perspectives and **experiences**. Such a rubric can assess the letter's entire impact on the reader in addition to the content's engagement, clarity, and relevance.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, I have always found it hard to meet the requirements of being a student. Ever since my years of high school, I really have no idea what professors are looking for to give good grades. When we choose to develop a productive skill, either Speaking or Writing, what we need to see from our students is effective production of the lesson's target language. This will usually include accurate use of the vocabulary or grammar being taught, effective communication of meaning and practical application to a real-life situation. If the student can perform well in all of these regards by the end of the lesson, then we can say that the learning process has been successful.

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